

Sr/Ca daily

Sr/Ca tidal

Mg/Ca daily

Mg/Ca tidal

Mn/Ca daily

Mn/Ca tidal

Ba/Ca daily

Ba/Ca tidal

colour

- TM29
- TM84
- TS85
- TSFRS1
- TSM1
- SQSA1
- PM2_1
- PM2_2
- PM3_1
- PM3_2
- PM4